

of heading were -0.932 for Sarikilçik, -0.973 for Krasnodorsky, -0.907 for Calrose, -0.944 for Gritna, and -0.835 for Basmati. Correlations between sterility and the lowest temperature to which plants were exposed during the 11 days before heading (generally accepted as the starting point of microsporogenesis) were -0.608 for Sarikilçik, -0.863 for Krasnodorsky, -0.475 for Calrose, -0.630 for Gritna, and -0.012 for Basmati. Negative correlations for sterility-lowest temperature on heading day were higher than those for sterility-lowest temperature exposure during 11 days before heading. Even if there is no cool injury during microsporogenesis, a temperature below critical (15°C) within 12 hours of heading (on the day or night preceding heading) causes high sterility of florets. This may be due to indehiscence of anthers and failure of pollen grain germination on the stigma.

The response to critical temperature (15°C) varied from variety to variety. Krasnodorsky, Gritna, and Sarikilçik were affected more than Calrose and Basmati. Rice breeding programs in Turkey should concentrate on cool temperature injury during flowering for a second crop production model, which seems possible only with very early cultivars. ■

Cold-tolerant variety VLK Dhan 39 released for Uttar Pradesh hills

V. S. Chauhan, scientist (Breeding), and J. P. Tandon, director, Vivekananda Parvatiya Krishi Anusandhan Shala, Almora-263601, U.P., India

Cold damage is the most serious constraint to rice yields in Northern India at altitudes up to 2200 meters. A highly cold-tolerant variety, VLK Dhan 39, recently was approved by the U.P. State Varietal Release Committee for cultivation in medium-altitude irrigated valleys.

VLK Dhan 39 — a pureline selection from China 1039/IR580-19-2-3-1, was isolated at Khudwani. It performed well in multilocational trials under the All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Programme. In 21 yield evaluation trials

Average yields for VLK Dhan 39 in Uttar Pradesh hills, India.^a

Variety	Yield (t/ha)				Mean
	1976 (2)	1977 (6)	1978 (5)	1979 (7)	
VLK Dhan 39	3.0	4.7	3.7	2.3	3.4
Thapachini	2.2	3.4	2.7	2.1	2.6
Increase over Thapachini (%)		37.8	37.6	10.4	31.4

^aValues in parentheses indicate the number of sites where yields were averaged.

and farmers' field demonstrations, it outyielded the local check Thapachini by 31%.

VLK Dhan 39 is early-maturing (115 days) compared to local varieties (130 days). Plants are semi-tall with medium tillering ability and good panicle exertion. Sheath color of basal leaves is predominantly light purple with a few pure

green plants. Florets have purple apiculi and the grains are medium long. It has a fair degree of tolerance for blast and stem borers. Its grain type and cooking quality are acceptable to local consumers.

VLK Dhan 39 gave an average yield of 3.4 t/ha, compared to 2.6 t/ha for Thapacini (see table). ■

Low temperature injury in some rice varieties

D. Jaya Raj, R. Vijayakumar, and J. P. Gaddipati, Rice Section, Agricultural Research Institute (ARI), Rajendranagar, Hyderabad, 500030, India.

Unexpected damage in rice variety trials at ARI in early 1981 has been attributed to cold injury. Variety trials were sown the first week of December 1980 and transplanted the first two weeks of January 1981. Seedlings were healthy and green until the beginning of February 1981, when the crop was at maximum tillering. But on 12 February the leaves of some varieties were found to have

turned dark yellow to light red (see table).

The damaged varieties were among entries in different trials. The symptoms were uniform in all replications. One parent is common in the parentage of some damaged varieties.

The symptom was uniform in a complete population of a variety, unlike the symptoms expected from disease, pests or nutritional disorder. Other varieties in the trials were green and healthy. Thus, the phenomenon appeared to be a case of cold injury.

The minimum low temperature was 18.1°C on 10 February and 9.6°C on 11 February. This sudden, extreme drop in temperature probably caused cold injury

Varieties showing low temperature damage at Hyderabad.

Variety	Parentage
IR36	IR1561-228//IR24-4/O.N//CR94-13
IR9828-81-2-3	IR2071-559//IR1820-52//IR36
IR13429-91-2-3	IR4432-53-33//PTB33//IR36
RNR31821	W1263/Tella Hamsa
RNR87877	IR34/Tella Hamsa
RNR98205	RP4-14//RNR29939
RNR99082	IR1514 AE 597/Tella Hamsa
RNR99101	IR1514 AE 597/Tella Hamsa
IET1318	IR139429-196-1
IET6148	Bala/Co 13
IET6228	IET2936/RP79-11//S ₂ S ₂
IET13969	IET1991/W 13801
BR161-28-25	Chandina/IR425-1-1-3-8-3
CR141-5035	N22/TNI//T90/IR8
CR157-22-1900	Vijayai/PTB 10
PK174-13-1-5	Basmati 370/IR95-1-5-3-2-2-2